

A School Exclusion-To- Youth Offending Pipeline.

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Abstract

This research study hypothesises that institutional discrimination contributes to an evidential school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. The 'school-to-prison pipeline' has been a term used within criminology which demonstrates the relationship between the education system and youth incarceration. The term argues that youth offending can be consequence to school policies which criminalise young people. In five chapters, this dissertation thematically discusses and analyses the perspectives of six British citizens to understand their experiences and opinions on a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. Following a qualitative approach, three parents and three young adults participated in semi-structured interviews to gain depth in understanding each perspective and experience. The study concludes that institutional discrimination is contributory to an evidential school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK particularly with race, gender, and disability-based discrimination. Analysis of interview data revealed new insights about lived experiences for young people involved. The study will also show that Black male youths with special educational needs are disproportionately affected by a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

This first chapter of the research paper is to introduce the problem being investigated, the purpose of this study, and the research question that will be answered. The problem investigated in this dissertation is a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. With purpose to view public perceptions on the matter, the hypothesis is that institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. The term 'pipeline' refers to the process by which some school students are likely to enter the criminal justice system due to school institutional practices, including school exclusion (Okilwa, Khalifa and Briscoe, 2017). It is argued that this is a failing of the education system, which needs to dismantle such institutional practices to prevent directing school students into the criminal justice system (Okilwa, Khalifa and Briscoe, 2017). The Equality Act 2010 outlines discrimination as the unfair treatment in relation to one or more of the eight protected characteristics: age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage and civil partnership, race, religion or belief, sex, and sexual orientation. Therefore, institutional discrimination is the discriminatory treatment towards a group of people or an individual that is conducted by institutions or society beyond personal prejudice (Thompson, 2020). In the UK, the concept of institutional discrimination was put in headlines in the public discourse around public services such as the education and criminal justice system by the 1999 Macpherson report. Following the 1993 racially motivated murder of Stephen Lawrence, the Macpherson report highlighted racism as not only individual, but 'institutional', thus resulting in failure of the Metropolitan Police to investigate Lawrence's murder (Macpherson, 1999).

This research study will address how race, gender, and disability based institutional discrimination contribute to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. The dissertation includes data within the past twenty years to demonstrate patterns and changes within the topic. In doing so, consistent, or inconsistent variables can be measured to provide a critical discussion. Moreover, the demographic focus is predominately Black youths, whilst still appreciating the effects on a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline amongst other race and ethnicities such as Gypsy and Roma in the literature review. The limited accessibility to the Gypsy and Roma community prohibits receiving their perceptions on the matter for this study. As this study will highlight some consequences of lack of social justice, the common theme throughout the dissertation is inequality. Although the amount of young people in youth custody has decreased by 79% compared with ten years ago, Black youths continue to be overrepresented in the statistics (YJB, 2023). Therefore, the significance of this research is that it correlates and investigates current criminal justice problems such as the overrepresentation

of Black youths. This study will cohere with existing studies such as the Perera study (2020) which analysed the racial bias throughout the education and criminal justice system. Additionally, this study relates to current data as the ONS (2022) reported that 72.2% of young people who received custodial sentences were temporarily excluded from school.

Four chapters follow: literature review, methodology, data analysis and conclusion. The literature review will highlight key literature that provide understanding on the topic and variables which contribute to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. The third chapter; the methodology, will explain how the primary research was conducted. This is to provide validity and clarity on the sample of the participants in this research in addition to noting possible improvements. The fourth chapter will be the findings and analysis of the data collected where findings from the data collected will also be discussed and compared to previous research. This will be done to draw attention to public perceptions on the matter and to investigate the hypothesis which is that institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. Chapter four is where direct quotes from participants will be used to support the findings. The fifth and final chapter is the conclusion which summarises all the chapters.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The hypothesis of the paper is that institutional discrimination contributes to an evidential link between school exclusions and youth offending in the UK. This chapter is a literature review where key research studies were analysed to view how their data explores the proposition. This chapter is divided into three main sections: race, gender, and special education needs (SEN). The first section looks at a study which identified race as one aspect of institutional discrimination contributing to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. The section lays out key findings of the chosen study while including arguments made by other scholars. The second section will focus on gender while linking the data to the first study discussed. Finally, the third section will feature literature demonstrating how SEN influences a correlation between the institutional practices in the education and youth crime system. Following these main sections, the conclusion will summarise the findings of the literature analysed. These studies were chosen as they interconnect thus demonstrating the complexities and intersectionality within the hypothesis. By the end of this chapter, a connection will be made on how race, gender and disability based institutional discrimination are influential factors in a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. Therefore, the following research studies are important in the dissertation because it gives a greater understanding on the topic.

2.2 Race and Ethnicity

4in 10 et al. (2020) conducted a research study by speaking with 'a small number' of parents whose child(ren) have experienced school exclusion, and young people with personal school exclusion experience on their opinions and encounters of formal school exclusions in London. They define school exclusions as both fixed term; a maximum of 45 days, and permanent; when a child can no longer return to that school (4in 10 et al., 2020). This study is included because it is relevant to the paper as it focused on school exclusion in the UK and its influence on youth crime. In the study, race and ethnicity were highlighted as key components in school exclusions due to the labelling and biases ethnic minority pupils were subject to by school policies and teachers (4in 10 et al., 2020). This is illustrated by the response of one student who said that the only non-White teacher in their school was 'the only one who understood' them (4in 10 et al., 2020). Further illustration of biases from the perception of parents was demonstrated in the quote of one parent:

“When Black children spoke loudly, they were shouted at, disciplined, and given a sanction. Whilst when the White children were being loud, they were not responded to in this way” (4in 10 *et al.*, 2020: 13).

This shows the parents’ perception of racial institutional discrimination causing the behaviour of school children to be monitored through unfair and discriminatory policies and viewpoints (4in 10 *et al.*, 2020). Supported by Kulz (2015) who carried out 26 face-to-face semi-structured interviews on the matter, the behaviour of ethnic minority children (commonly Black children), is criminalised and sexualised, thus responded to as that of a rationale adult. This supports the concept of ‘adultification bias’ towards ethnic minorities where Black students are treated more harshly than their peers of other ethnic groups. Moreover, Gypsy and Roma, and Black Caribbeans having the highest rate of permanent exclusions in 2018 and 2019 supports the parents’ perception because it displays discrepancies in the distribution of school exclusion because of race and ethnicity (4in 10 *et al.*, 2020). While academics such as Kulz (2015) and Papa (2020) support the suggestions by citing racist assumptions as a vital feature in the high rate of permanent exclusions for Black boys, there is limited data on the reason(s) why Gypsy and Roma students have a high rate of permanent exclusions. This implies that although 4in 10 *et al.* (2020) touch on key features in the school exclusion of Black students, the research study is limited in exploring the high exclusion rates for pupils of other race and ethnicities.

4in 10 *et al.* (2020) link school exclusions to youth criminality through finding that 89% of children in young offender institutions in England and Wales had been excluded in 2018. This is important as the high percentage upholds an association between school exclusions and youth offending. 4in 10 *et al.* (2020) discussing race as a component in a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline is proven significant because although the Black 10–17-year-old population in England and Wales was at 4% in the census data of 2011, Black youths are still overrepresented in the youth justice system (Fraser, 2022). As Black children are excluded the most, they are also the most overrepresented in the youth justice system. Likewise, where certain ethnic groups like Chinese youths are underrepresented in school exclusion rates, they are also underrepresented in the youth justice system (ONS, 2022). The similarities are noteworthy because it stresses the consistency between school exclusion figures and youth criminality figures based on race. This is seen in comments by scholars such as Bell (2021) who stated that generally, the behaviour of Black people is watched more prominently than other race of people. Their argument stems from a study which involved 160 qualitative interviews with Black high school pupils about their high school experience in Detroit along with interviews from parents and teachers (Bell, 2021). This said oversurveillance of young Black people encourages a stereotype of them

being more likely to engage in unwanted behaviour and criminality hence, implemented strategies to manage assumed behaviour thus high rates of Black youths in school exclusions and youth crime statistics.

Additionally, 4in 10 et al. (2020) indicated that being excluded from school leaves children vulnerable to being exploited as the process for criminals to coerce, threaten, and/or manipulate their involvement in criminal activity such as county lines becomes easier. On the flip side, they also argued that victims of child criminal exploitation became more at risk of school exclusions due to the criminals' need to continue the child exploitation, therefore controlling the child's behaviour into behaviour that warrants school exclusion (4in 10 et al., 2020). This is validated by the NCA (2017) who reported Black youths as the most prominent young county line victims in London although it varied from city to city. Such variation could be accredited to London having the highest population of Black Africans and Black Caribbeans in England and Wales (Ethnicity Facts and Figures, 2022). This underlines the possibility of London based studies like 4in 10 et al. (2020) having methodological problems in generalising a pipeline across the UK due to possible bias produced by the geographical location of the study.

Despite this, 4in 10 et al. (2020) supports the hypothesis of this dissertation because the study drew on 'institutional racism' as one form of institutional discrimination influencing a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline through direct opinions of parents and young people as well as racial similarities in school exclusions and youth crime statistics. A strength of this research study is the discussion on intersectionality thus considering how intersectionality changes the dynamics of a pipeline. The research therefore appreciated race as a multi-faceted factor contributing to a school exclusion-youth offending pipeline because additional factors such as class that would illuminate in more depth the marginalisation of Black youths were explored. However, the research failed to discuss gender within the demonstration of intersectionality. This is a weakness because the DfE (2020) stated that there is a difference in exclusion rates between Black boys and Black girls with Black boys being excluded at a higher rate. In youth crime statistics only 2% of children in remand are female thus indicating further consistency between school exclusions and youth crime in the UK (YJB, 2022).

2.3 Gender

Carlile (2009) carried out a participant observation research study throughout several schools in 'Enway' over the course of two years. This research looked at gender and the intersection it had with school exclusions by observing gender in same-sex and single-gendered schools. Carlile conducting the research over a two-year period is helpful as the findings are in-depth and therefore arguably more

valid. The research study of Carlile (2009) defined exclusions as the permanent removal of a student from their school. Carlile (2009) stated that gender shapes school exclusions because there is a difference in the policing of behaviour based on gender within the schools studied. Labels placed on both male and female students were cited as featuring factors that shaped difference in response to behaviour (Carlile, 2009). Boys were labelled as aggressive and troublesome while girls were labelled as sensitive and weak (Carlile, 2009). Consequently, these gender stereotypes created distinct treatments between male and female school students. They found that gender stereotyping strengthened tolerable and anticipated behaviour for girls and boys hence variations in repercussions (NEU, 2019). An example of this was seen in the disparity in response between boys and girls who sexually harassed in school because response to perpetrators of sexual harassment was intensified when a female student targeted a male student as that behaviour by girls contradicts their gendered labels (Carlile, 2009). Carlile (2009) also observed gender stereotyping working both ways as some boys were disciplined more quickly and harshly than girls because of the 'strong' and 'intimidating' labels placed on boys. Carlile's overall findings of differential gendered practices are confirmed as 15% of boys in mixed-sex schools said they experienced difference in treatment based on their gender compared to 36% of girls (NEU, 2019).

Moreover, Agenda et al., (2021) carried out interviews with fourteen girls and women with experience of mainstream school exclusions along with desk-based research and a roundtable discussion with ten experts in the field (Agenda et al., 2021). The gender imbalance in school exclusion rates was noticeable in their study as girls were more likely than boys to be informally excluded and therefore lost in school exclusion data (Agenda et al., 2021). This means, the rate at which girls were excluded was often underestimated and arguably, the needs of female school students unmet (Agenda et al., 2021). Carlile (2009) also compared the marginalisation of Black female students to White female students stating that Black female students were disciplined more than White female students. Agenda et al., (2022) supports this by highlighting that in the academic year 2019/2020, Black Caribbean girls were excluded at double the rate of White British girls. Significantly, the findings showcase intersectionality within gender based institutional discrimination. Like 4 in 10 et al., (2020), Carlile's findings are limited by not exploring the distinction between Black Caribbean girls and Black African girls which would produce further understanding on the intricacies of institutional discrimination. Moreover, Agenda et al., (2022) reported that Gypsy and Roma girls were excluded at the highest rate of all female students which is relevant because it links back in the discussion of race and ethnicity and again appreciates intersectionality. This however limits Carlile (2009) because there is restricted discussion on the Gypsy and Roma community in school hence Carlile's research could not be used to highlight the reason for

the high rates in exclusion for Gypsy and Roma girls and boys. This could be credited to Carlile recruiting the sample via schools although Gypsy and Roma pupils continue to have low school attendance and therefore, arguably high exclusion rates (Ethnicity Facts and Figures, 2023). However, in the Greason and Shallice (2017) report, several reasons for the high rate of Gypsy and Roma exclusions were underlined such as lack of school representation for Gypsy and Roma pupils, lack of viewing Gypsy and Roma individuals as a part of an ethnic group, and little training for teachers to understand the Gypsy and Roma community. This influences behaviour-based exclusions for Gypsy and Roma pupils because certain acceptable behaviour in the Gypsy and Roma community is misinterpreted by teachers, hence logged as persistent disruptive behaviour (Greason and Shallice, 2017). For example, as Gypsy and Roma young boys are seen as adults in their community, they are expected to engage in direct conversation with their elders although this can be seen as confrontational towards teachers lacking understanding of the Gypsy and Roma community (Greason and Shallice, 2017).

Since the dissertation intends to answer how institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK, Carlile's study (2009) related to the aim of the research because it found that boys were excluded at a higher rate and made up more than 75% of the youth custody figures. Carlile (2009) insinuated that higher exclusion rates for girls would mean they become disaffected more hence, the possibility of their rate of criminality increasing as disaffection from school leaves pupils vulnerable to low GCSE grades, free time if excluded, and frustrated with the education system. Boys are overrepresented in the youth offending population because they make up for 51% of the youth population in England and Wales but 87% of the youth offending population (YJB, 2022). The gender-based institutional discrimination affects a school exclusions-to-youth offending pipeline because just as girls represent a substantially smaller percentage of children excluded from school, it accounts for children in youth custody too (Carlile, 2009). Gender-based institutional discrimination is argued by Carlile (2009) as influential because of the noticeable gender difference in both school exclusions and youth offending statistics. This argument compliments 4in 10 et al., (2020) as they noted that those overrepresented in school exclusion statistics, were also overrepresented in youth custody figures. Additionally, those involved in criminal activities such as county lines as highlighted by 4in 10 et al., (2020) are often boys, thus creating further connections as they are also excluded the most (Carlile, 2009).

2.4 Special Educational Needs (SEN)

The Children and Families Act 2014 defines special educational needs (SEN) as:

“a learning difficulty or disability which calls for special educational provision to be made” (*Act 2014*, s. 20).

This needs to be considered alongside the wider policy legal framework clarified by the Office for Disability Issues (2013), which states that the legal requirements of the Equality Act 2010 are intended to dovetail with the education SEN framework, so SEN will be looked at here as a ‘disability’ in a broad sense. Therefore, this section of the literature review will cover how disability-based institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK.

Kulz (2015) carried out a qualitative research study over the course of nine months from March 2014. The study consisted of 26 face-to-face semi-structured interviews using three key groups of participants: parents of excluded school children, local authority exclusion officers, and headteachers (Kulz, 2015). Kulz’s research study (2015) found that there was a significant link between school exclusions and SEN. The study found that this was due to the lack of SEN support in mainstream school causing SEN to be translated as bad behaviour, and SEN students becoming overwhelmed because of unmet educational needs (Kulz, 2015). The study featured many stories from parents who explained that the needs of their excluded child were overlooked as SEN assessments did not take place (Kulz, 2015). Moreover, Kulz’s study (2015) also identified the importance of intersectionality by discussing ‘continuing inequalities’ and acknowledging complexities and overlaps of disadvantage for some SEN pupils such as Black and/or working-class SEN pupils. This draws similarities to 4in 10 et al (2020) and Carlile (2009), because both studies touch on intersectionality and the intricacy of looking at discrimination within school exclusion figures. Additionally, the head teachers interviewed by Kulz (2015) underlined the disadvantage SEN students have due to the performance measures which shape acceptable and unacceptable behaviour in classrooms. Parents and headteachers’ responses showcased performance targets as one of the main reasons for high exclusion rates of SEN students due to the system effecting teaching styles (Kulz, 2015). A teacher who takes a student-centred approach can shift to teacher-centred by focusing on reaching performance targets rather than supporting the needs of the children, thus exacerbating academic stress (especially for SEN pupils), hence effecting student behaviour (Kulz, 2015). Recent findings from the Department for Education (DfE) accommodated these perspectives as children identified with SEN with an education, health, and care plan (EHC) were excluded on a fixed-term basis the most at a rate of 6.37 in the 2021/2022 spring term (DfE, 2023). Those who did not have an EHC plan but had SEN were temporarily excluded at the second highest rate with 6.31 (DfE, 2023). This differs from the rate of pupils with no SEN who were temporarily excluded at a rate of 1.66 in the 2021/2022 spring term (DfE, 2023). Moreover, pupils who

had SEN, but no EHC plan received the highest rate of permanent exclusions with a rate of 0.08 compared to 0.02 for those with no SEN (DfE, 2023). These figures demonstrate a significantly higher school exclusion rate for SEN children while illustrating the impact of an EHC plan. It insinuates that EHC plans explicitly support the needs of SEN pupils thus decreasing unwanted behaviour which is evident in the lower exclusion rates. This supports Kulz's (2015) findings because the lack of SEN support resulting in unmet needs translated in unwanted behaviour was emphasized.

Kulz's study relates to youth criminality because almost 80% of people who received a custodial sentence were identified with SEN at some stage within their schooling from the academic year ending 2003 to 2010 (ONS, 2022). Kulz (2015) argued that the education system fails in accommodating SEN students hence higher exclusion rates of SEN pupils. As a result, youths with SEN are often disaffected from education resulting in less respect towards authority (Kulz, 2015). Feeling marginalised and alienated from education and society then causes SEN pupils to become more vulnerable in developing depression and low self-esteem thus constructing a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline as 'the road they make up is often perilous' (Kulz, 2015). This is validated by one participant of the study who stated:

"The boys who have nothing to lose who are not in school - they will carry a gun, will fire the gun, because they now have to make up their own road" (Kulz, 2015: 91).

Overall, the findings echoed the role of disability-based institutional discrimination in a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. This is because before exclusion takes place, disability-based discrimination is done through lack of SEN identification and support hence unreasonable expectations and disciplining of SEN students.

2.5 Conclusion

To conclude, the literature review suggested that race, gender, and disability based institutional discrimination influence a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. Seen through the opinions of participants interviewed in the studies and further supported by statistics, the literature review touched on adultification and disaffection which increases vulnerability to youth crime involvement. Furthermore, this chapter is important to the research study because it provides insight on the research data and viewpoints already available. The similar themes throughout each literature indicate a consistency in the point that; what effects the school experience, also effects youth

criminality. Therefore, carrying out independent research will help elaborate further on the topic within the literature discussed. However, before exploring the findings of the independent research conducted, it is important to present the methodology for readers to understand the methods used to reach the conclusion that will soon be discussed.

Chapter 3: Methodology

This chapter of the research paper will discuss the methodology used in collecting data of the public perceptions on a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. It is important to discuss the methodology because it allows readers to assess the validity of the data and analysis in this dissertation (Kuada, 2012). Additionally, this chapter is helpful in examining the strengths and weaknesses throughout the research process and how these influence the data collected (Kuada, 2012). This chapter will begin with discussing the research type chosen to collect data. In doing so, the advantages and disadvantages exhibited will justify the decided research method for the research study. Secondly, the original plan of data collection will be discussed and compared to the final execution of data collection. This is to map out the changes that were made and explain why these were suitable. Finally, what went well and what was learned throughout the methodology of this paper will be considered to underline improvements for future research.

The methodology chosen for this research was primary research which is the collection of new information and new data through several methods such as surveys, interviews, and focus groups (University of Southampton, 2023). This differs from secondary research which is the collection of second-hand information (University of Southampton, 2023). Primary research was chosen as the most suited methodology for this paper because it provided the ability to create questions correlating with the aim of the paper (University of Southampton, 2023). As the paper intends to investigate the hypothesis, institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK, the method of primary research chosen was semi-structured interviews, a one-to-one qualitative research method used to create discussion through a set of some predetermined questions (Lyons and Coyle, 2007). Semi-structured interviews were the appropriate type of interview because it is a medium between structured and unstructured interviews. This was important to the research topic because it maximised the advantages of all three interview methods while considering the disadvantages. Moreover, semi-structured interviews held strength in delving deeper into unique experiences in a safe manner (Lyons and Coyle, 2007). This differs from focus groups; qualitative method in which questions are asked to a group of people, which was considered as a method of data collection (Gill *et al.*, 2008). Focus groups had advantages over semi-structured interviews because it is time effective and creates discussion which in turn provides rich data to analyse (Gill *et al.*, 2008). However, semi-structured interviews highlighted more advantages for this research as focus groups could pressure participants to answer a certain way, create hesitation to share certain experiences

which restricts the data collected and creates an unsafe environment (Gill et., 2008). As the questions require participants to recall past experiences, semi structured interviews were deemed more appropriate because it creates privacy and confidentiality thus eliminating the risk of harm to participants (Lyons and Coyle, 2007). Qualitative research was a desirable methodological approach because the experience of each responder was given value to, thus allowing an understanding in the variety of answers (Stake, 2010). Meaning, if this research was not done qualitatively, there would be restriction in analysing responses because a quantitative methodological approach would answer 'what' respondents thought of a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline, without acknowledging 'why'. Answering 'why' participants had certain perspectives was vital because it allowed participants to underline issues instead of the researcher. This is beneficial to the study as the openness of qualitative research increased the validity of research findings by decreasing possible bias from the researcher (Stake, 2010). As a result, the authenticity and safety of all parties involved in the research was amplified.

Decreasing possible risk of harm to research participants was understood and respected through the ethical guidelines of the British Society of Criminology (2023) and the Economic and Social Research Council (2023). Regarding sampling, the original plan was to have six participants; three young adults and three parents who currently have or have had children in secondary school in the last five years. Having an equal number of young adults and parents was important in exploring public perception on a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK because as participants varied in age, they also varied in experience hence creating the opportunity to have an array of data to analyse. One of the young adults envisaged was a current offender in custody. It was anticipated that further diversity within the data collected would be provided as their experience with offending correlated with the purpose of this paper. However, not all the compulsory actions to safeguard the participant and the researcher could be met. Through the ethical guidelines of the British Society of Criminology (2023), the Economic and Social Research Council (2023), and discussions with the assigned supervisor, it was recognised that terminating the potential involvement of this participant would safeguard all parties within the research process. As the participant agreed to the possibility of their involvement, the reasoning for discontinuing that possibility was explained to respect and acknowledge their willingness to contribute. As a result, another young adult was asked to participate in the research to retain an equal number of young adults and parents. Moreover, twelve interview questions was the original plan set with four of those twelve questions exclusive to the young adults and the parents. Twelve interview questions were chosen because it was enough to explore and understand the research topic from the perspectives of each participant. Each interview was arranged to be conducted in person so that the

observation of each interviewees body language could take place to notice things such as discomfort during the interview (Johnson, Scheitle and Ecklund, 2019). As a researcher this is important because of the responsibility to reduce distress to everyone involved in the research process (Economic and Social Research Council, 2023). Additionally, in person interviews were organised to better encourage a high level of engagement throughout the duration of each interview (Johnson, Scheitle and Ecklund, 2019). In person interviews did not go to plan for all participants as only two interviews were conducted in person because the additional four participants needed to reschedule. Consequently, four interviews were held virtually to guarantee enough time to analyse each interview. Although the virtual interviews decreased the ability to view body language properly, it was time effective, and precautions were still put in place to protect all those involved and encourage their engagement. For example, asking “is it okay to continue” permitted interviewees to take their time and pause where necessary. Additionally, looking at the camera, nodding, and making minimal responses were utilised as a researcher to motivate interviewees to speak freely.

To improve future research, more time would be given to plan the methodology thus factoring in unexpected reschedules and allowing the original plan to still be implemented. It has been learned that the envisage of certain participants should be planned more effectively before asking for their consent to avoid unwanted feelings that may arise from being a discontinued participant. In future research, providing more time to plan the methodology would also permit maximised appreciation for the significance each participant brings to the research. For example, assessing the significance of having a participant who is a current teaching assistant in secondary school appreciated the experience this participant would bring to investigating the hypothesis. Therefore, more time to plan would enable assessing such factors for all participants. Regardless of the challenges, each interview ran smoothly which is credited to the invite email sent out before the interview process. In each invitation, the purpose and structure of the interviews were stated with the confidentiality and rights of the interviewees expressed. Furthermore, the number of participants, number of interview questions, estimated interview time, and reason for the chosen group of interviewees was displayed within the invitation. This was done to support interviewees to feel free in asking questions before, after, and during the interview as well as supporting their right to withdraw their participation or pause where necessary. The interview invitation also helped with the high level of engagement in each interview as the expected duration of the interviews enabled everyone to accept participation while understanding the interview structure. Without the interview invitation, participants would not know the purpose and structure of the interview process thus minimising the chances of their contribution.

To conclude, the methodology has taught that planning is an essential part of researching as it minimises issues within the data collection and analysis process (Kuada, 2012). This is because planning enables the aims and objectives of the paper to be defined and organised thus influencing a successful and organised research project (Kuada, 2012). Additionally, flexibility is an important skill to have as a researcher because it allows researchers to adapt to changes and continue the research process as not everything goes to plan, and all participants are different. Without the skill of flexibility during the methodological process, researching becomes more stressful and overwhelming which in turn can minimise the potential, or prohibit the completion of the research project. Moreover, this chapter has suggested that a qualitative approach was best suited to collect data.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis

4.1 Introduction

The overall aim of this study was to determine if the public perceive institutional discrimination as contributory to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. Therefore, this fourth chapter discusses the data analysis and findings of the qualitative study. The interviews conducted in this research were recorded and transcribed to analyse the data thematically. Thematic analysis was carried out through familiarising with the transcripts, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, and defining and naming the themes (Caulfield and Hill, 2018). Therefore, insight on the perspectives of all participants were displayed with two main themes noted and five sub-themes. The first main theme is institutional discrimination, which was highlighted throughout the research and will be elaborated into three sub-themes that emerged amongst interviewees' concerns related to the broader theme: race, gender, and special educational needs (SEN). The second main theme is 'under the radar', that is further analysed into two sub-themes: 'ongoing issues', and 'pupil referral units (PRUs)' as these sub-themes were consistently discussed as relevant to participants, while also being interconnected with the first theme of institutional discrimination. This chapter will show that although answers to the twelve questions asked varied, all participants shared a consensus perspective on the research question and arguably agreed with the hypothesis: institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK.

4.2 Institutional Discrimination

Institutional discrimination is the discriminatory treatment towards a group of people or an individual that is conducted by institutions or society beyond personal prejudice (Thompson, 2020). Experiences of institutional discrimination contributing to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline was clear in interviewee accounts, as discrimination was a major theme throughout the responses of each participant. The three sub-themes below were important in the account of all participants in relation to their experience and perspectives about the main issue. This section will analyse how each sub-theme was regarded as influential in a school exclusion-to-offending pipeline by interviewees. Additionally, it is noteworthy that participants conceptualised discrimination in these accounts as the disparity of treatment within the educational system based on race, gender, and special educational needs (SEN). The Office for Disability Issues (2013), as noted earlier, explains that SEN can be regarded as a disability as the Equality Act 2010 and the Children and Families Act 2014 has legal requirements intended to dovetail with the SEN structure.

4.2.1 Special Educational Needs (SEN)

Participants felt that when a young person 'doesn't fit' the acceptable behaviour set by school policies, rules, and the law, they get into trouble. Although in theory interviewees see no issue with the principle of disciplining unacceptable behaviour, the issue arises in practice due to the subjective and often bias viewpoint of interpreting acceptable behaviour in exercising school policies, rules, and the law. This is because participants feel institutional discrimination is ingrained in the perspective of acceptable behaviour whether in smaller scales like a school, or larger scales like the entire youth justice system.

The term 'neglected' was used by respondents as interviewees felt that when punishing behaviour, the child's 'needs and differences' are not considered. This is seen in the response of one parent: *"looking at it from an SEN background we get loads of kids from mainstream schools who have been excluded and it affects their learning, the impact is affecting their learning, its affecting them socially, its affecting them morally, its affecting them because these kids wanna be around their peers, they wanna be around the education system but because they're misunderstood because of their behaviour – they [teachers] see it as a behaviour problem but we [SEN teaching assistants] see it's a communication problem."* The dash in this quote indicates the participant interjecting with their thought by stressing that the problems SEN children have within the education system is not behavioural, it is communication at the fault of the teachers. This interjection is of great relevance because it exhibits that participants perceive SEN as a significant issue impacting the school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline due to the disaffection experienced from the misinterpretation of their behaviour. Moreover, when asked "does having learning support make a difference in pupil behaviour", it was vital for participants to stress the importance of understanding that the discussion is about children which makes it 'unfair' for teachers to assume young people have the words to 'truly express themselves' especially if they are SEN children. This touches on adultification which emerged throughout the interviews as it was felt that disadvantage students were not often viewed as children by their teachers but rather 'adults who know what they're doing'.

Such is like Kulz's findings in the literature review who expressed the behaviour of children from ethnic minorities is often criminalised instead of being viewed as 'childish mistakes' (Kulz, 2015). One parent interviewed said that too many children do not know they have SEN which makes it more 'annoying' for the child excluded because they will self-criticise and self-judge thus adding to disaffection from school. Supported by Kulz (2015), lack of SEN support is one main factor in high exclusion rates for SEN pupils because teachers fail to recognise and accommodate additional needs thus causing frustration from unmet needs for the child. This sub-theme interconnects with the two upcoming sub-themes as SEN accounts in a context of race and gender. There was a clear consensus among participants who felt

that male and Black students were more likely as SEN students to be neglected by the education system due to race and gender-based discrimination. Importance in noting this is because it emphasises the discriminatory layers, which affects conclusions about the hypothesis. A quote by parent one highlights the complexities of looking at institutional discrimination saying *“for Black children they don’t receive much learning support because they have so many gaps of misunderstanding Black children’s behaviour, they don’t follow them to recognise. It starts in primary school they don’t focus on them. There’s a lot of neglect towards Black kids, they don’t focus to see like if the child is dyslexic or autistic or has learning difficulties.”* The impact of race is the same throughout each interview when determining how institutional discrimination influences a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline.

4.2.2 Race

When discussing race, participants referred to Black Africans and Black Caribbeans as ‘Black’ unless they differentiated between the two ethnicities. For all three young adults interviewed they stated that in their year, they only recall Black students being excluded from school. This is displayed by adult three who said *“Black girls. Those were the only girls that were excluded, absolutely every single one of them. There’s not a single White girl in my year or Latino, Hispanic whatever even Asian in my year that had ever been excluded in my entire time being at secondary school. It was predominately Africans, actually it was just Africans I don’t think we had a Caribbean girl excluded, no we didn’t it just Africans”*. The difference between Black African and Black Caribbean girls contrasts findings in the literature review specifically in sections 2.1 and 2.2 as only Black Caribbean girls were discussed as Black girls with high exclusion rates. This quote emphasises intersectionality within a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline while spotlighting race as an independent variable in a said pipeline. Evidently, the race of students remained the same for the other young adults who shared that in their experience, Black students were excluded noticeably more than any other race. This finding supports and refines the hypothesis: institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. The contribution of institutional racism within school exclusions was further stressed by adult one who said, *“all the young people I saw get excluded in my school were Black, I didn’t see no White people get excluded (laughs) I didn’t see not one White person being excluded”*. When asked why she laughed, adult two discussed feeling ‘disappointed but not surprised’ in realising only Black students were excluded in her experience.

The racial bias within a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline highlighted by the participants draws similarities to 4in 10 et al (2020) as they found that Black students were disproportionately affected by both youth crime and school exclusions. Their study drew the same connection made by

the participants: disproportionately excluding Black kids partly explains the overrepresentation of Black children in the youth justice system (4 in 10 *et al.*, 2020). The strength of the findings is that it reinforces and strengthens the hypothesis by drawing similarities to previous findings. Participants linked institutional discrimination within school exclusions to youth offending as they expressed that being excluded leaves a child 'more vulnerable'. One adult said that Black kids getting excluded the most leaves them at the highest risk to be 'angry' at the education system which links to disaffection from school and the chance to meet people who have had the same experience and are now 'into criminality to make money and do something with their time'. This is reiterated by parent two clarifying the pipeline saying, *"of course they will commit a crime because they don't know any better, they just know what they're being taught: 'I'm rejected, I can't get into a better school, I'm less privileged'. They have that stigma in their mind so they're coming out with the mindset that they're not wanted"*. From the responses of participants, it was made clear that race influences a pipeline between school exclusions and youth crime. However, the 'institutional discrimination' sub-theme of gender indicated very mixed perspectives & experiences. This is seen in participants' views of adultification as it was agreed that Black youths are adultified with difference in adultification between Black girls and Black boys thus arguably actualising the notion of a pipeline because of the disaffection. Young adult one illustrates the perception of adultification saying *"if we think about what skills training teachers should have, I think they definitely need to have adultification training because of what happened to Child Q in Hackney...that is an issue that happens with young people, young people, especially young people of ethnic minority are being seen as adults and being treated as adults when they are a young person"*. Child Q refers to the Child Q Case where an investigation into the police strip search of a teenage Black girl in secondary school highlighted 'adultification bias' and racism as 'likely' factors in the incident (Hackney, 2022).

4.2.3 Gender

Gender-based discrimination was presented as another consensus theme among participants, but there were diverse perspectives on the way in which they explained it was relevant. Parents who were interviewed felt boys received harsher punishments than girls and were viewed to be 'intimidating', 'bad' and 'troublesome' by teachers. Also, as expressed by two of the young adults, boys in secondary school were given less chances whereas girls were given more chances due to being viewed as 'weak' and 'sensitive' by teachers. However, adult three felt that girls were sometimes treated more intolerantly due to sexism saying, *"there's almost that expectation that boys will be boys like 'yeah you'll be rough or whatever but if a girls gonna do that, absolutely not that's un-lady like that's not feminine, get her out of here, she's a danger to society'. I feel like it's easier for girls to be written off compared to*

boys who will be given ample amount of chances.” From this quote, it is inferred that the gender stereotyping of girls leaves female students at risk of harsher punishment due to breaking the expectation of female behaviour. This quote supports the double deviance theory which states if a female commits a crime (or in this case breaks school policies), she will be treated harsher than a male as she is doubly deviant by breaking the school policy and gender stereotypes (Marsh *et al.*, 2011). This was contrasted by multiple participants observing that boys were treated harsher than girls in their experience thus underlining gender as a more complex form of discrimination than race in this data analysis. Adult one and adult two shared that ‘it was always Black boys’ who got excluded thus displaying a continuation of discrimination against Black students although the perception and experience of gender discrimination as shown above was complex. For adult one who went to a mixed-sex school, her answer to the question “who was most likely to get excluded and get excluded the most” was “*Black boys, it was always Black boys*”. When asked for characteristics, adult two who went to an all-boys school quickly stated “*Black boys, Black boys. Yeah*” again presenting a continuation of discrimination against Black students although the perception and experience of gender discrimination as shown above was complex. This was further noticeable when parent three said “*I don’t think that girls get treated differently than boys*” despite the two remaining parents believing that boys receive harsher punishment in school and in youth crime. Consequently, the way in which gender-based discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline remains questionable based on these participants diverse perspectives.

4.3 Under the Radar

‘Under the radar’ means something which is unnoticed or paid very little attention to (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023). It was a main emergent theme viewed as important amongst respondents and it pays closer attention to issues both inside and outside schools, that are also affected by institutional discrimination, and which arguably influences a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. Like the theme of discrimination, ‘Under the Radar’ will be split into two sub-themes that offer insights to pupils’ subjective experiences: ‘Ongoing issues’, and ‘Pupil referral units (PRUs)’. Interview participants expressed that the consequences of experiencing any one of the two subthemes are not touched on enough by teachers or youth justice authorities. Therefore, respondents feel acknowledging how such experiences affect a child could help minimise the pipeline.

4.3.1 ‘Ongoing Issues’

‘Ongoing issues’ was a strong theme that emerged from the interviews as participants felt it influences school exclusions and criminality. Interviewees described ongoing issues as relations between students

and responsibilities at home; problems that could be vital in their experience of the common school exclusion reason: disruptive behaviour. Participants felt schools were not doing enough for students' well-being especially in circumstances such as bullying. Bullying was an important topic brought up with some saying being a victim of bullying is when a young person is at risk of offending because 'teachers don't do enough' to combat bullying thus leaving young people to 'take it into their own hands'. This circles back to adultification because in their experience, participants were treated older than their age hence what they explained as reasoning for the teacher's minimal intervention in these 'ongoing issues'. The young adults felt teachers did not intercede earlier enough with students to prevent student fights that led to school exclusions, whereas parents felt teachers did not communicate with the parents about the 'ongoing issues in school' to prevent escalations that resulted in school exclusions. This is helpful for this research because it is an issue that the literature review does not cover thus also indicating that a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline is complex because of the elements involved. This idea was supported by adult one who told a story explaining that one boy was being teased and when he stood up for himself, he got excluded for unacceptable behaviour which she feels was 'unfair' as the boy was the victim. Adult one further explained that she believes because the victim was a Black boy, and the bully was a White boy, institutional discrimination tarnished how the bullying was responded to hence exacerbating the likeliness of criminality by the victim. Adult one's story is supported by Bell (2021) who theorised that the behaviour of Black students is watched more prominently than any other students. Although initially at odds with the findings about early lack of attention from teachers around SEN for Black children, it reiterates the points made by participants, Kulz (2015) and 4in 10 et al (2020); that Black students are watched more carefully regarding 'unwanted behaviour' but not regarding their 'needs'. Echoed by parent three *"when the behaviour changes in school, instead of the school seeing they haven't helped enough, they pick up that child as bad, fighting a lot, making noise in the school and not focusing in the lesson"*. This links to the story of the young adult implying the school watched the boy for bad behaviour but did not investigate the reasoning for the behaviour.

4.3.2 Pupil Referral Unit (PRU)

Pupil referral units (PRUs) is a type of school provision for young students in the UK who cannot attend mainstream school for different reasons, including being permanently excluded from their mainstream school (Okilwa, Khalifa and Briscoe, 2017). PRU was a sub-theme in this study because the participants made clear that in their experience, schools did not consider the effects of attending a PRU before and after they excluded a pupil. There was a consensus amongst participants that it was a negative experience and PRUs were freely described as a 'prison'. This is of high importance because there were

no questions posed to the interviewees about PRUs specifically although the negative impact it has on young people in the UK was raised as important by participants throughout the research. Referring to PRU as prison has also arguably clearly indicated the participants recognition of a school exclusion-to-offending pipeline in the UK for young people. It was expressed that there were multiple reasons a PRU would negatively affect a young person and increase their risk of criminality. One reason touched on the social learning theory which theorises social behaviour as learnt through observation and imitation of those around you (Pritchard and Woolard, 2010). One young adult said *“if discarded children all get together, what happens? You form your own community and if you’re all exhibiting behavioural issues stemming from God knows what, we’re all gonna encourage each other to do what you want, like no one is gonna be the voice of reason in that because no one cares so why should I? So it is easy, very easy for you to get groomed into stuff, it’s very easy for you to start committing crimes, it’s very easy for you to have no reason to behave in a way that’s socially acceptable because you’re not accepted as it is anyway so what benefit would I have doing stuff to please society but when I do try I’m in trouble, when I don’t try I’m in trouble, at every turn you’re telling me you don’t want me here.”* This stresses a process of entering criminality through imitation and disaffection from school which supports Bandura’s social learning theory. Theorising that new behaviour is created through observation, modelling and imitation reinforced by other people, the process of school exclusions encourages children to copy the messages being received about themselves which is relevant to some aspect of what goes on in the pipeline process (Pritchard and Woolard, 2010). This supports Kulz’s study (2015) as it reiterates the construction of a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline through disaffection.

Moreover, the word ‘groomed’ supports 4in 10 et al (2020) report of excluded children being more vulnerable to manipulation for involvement in county lines as the manipulation starts from grooming. This links to another reason given, which was the geographical location of the PRUs with one respondent describing as ‘often in gang affiliated areas’. Consequently, pupils were around gangs and people who would advertise criminality in a way that the young person thought was beneficial for them due to the disaffection from school which begins a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline. Moreover, participants felt that young people sent to PRUs after being excluded often embark on a self-fulfilling prophecy, believing they are as bad as their school experience has made them out to be, again supporting the social learning theory. Feeling ‘neglected’, ‘angry’, ‘frustrated’ and ‘over it’ means the young person becomes disaffected from school and interested in crime because the young person is usually not of legal age to have a job to make money. Therefore, as school is often the only thing occupying young people below the age of 16, being ‘discarded’ from school, ‘frustrated at everything’, unable to work, and vulnerable influences the belief that they must enter criminality to make money and occupy their time.

Reiterated from adult two who had been to a PRU was expressed through this quote: *“why would I? Why would I keep going to school? Why would I? Why would I trust in the system? When all they did was feed me to the dogs, why would I do that? Geographically, mentally, and emotionally are the main impacts of exclusion. If you don’t have encouragement and guidance, you’re just gonna be like ‘well I don’t think I can get anywhere in life so I’m just gonna do what I want, like if someone bullies me, I’m just gonna handle it cause what’s the point anyway,’ it can affect you negatively depending on the situation. If I’m getting bullied, I’m in a PRU, I can’t go any lower than this, so I’m gonna behave however I wanna behave because you’re not gonna kick me out of this PRU, I’m here because I got kicked out of school. There’s no positives, no real positive thing that comes out of going to a PRU. Nobody should be getting sent there, nobody.”* This quote represents the perspective on PRUs for all respondents as this was the stance across each interview where PRU was mentioned. Referring to PRUs as being ‘fed to the dogs’ emphasises the negative perspective adult two has on school exclusions and its impact on young people. This illustration of the consensus about PRUs captures participants perspective on key processes involved in a pipeline of school and criminality, as well as capturing the depth of feeling and emotional impact experienced. It also constitutes a dimension that was in the literature review. Participants perceived school exclusion as a racial, gendered and SEN issue as it was mostly Black boys often with SEN getting excluded thus ending up in PRUs. Moreover, respondents viewed PRUs as the start of a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline due to the disaffection and heightened vulnerability experienced.

4.4 Discussion

Through the perspectives and experiences of participants that emerged from the analysis above, a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK is a process heavily influenced by institutional discrimination. Participants expressed that institutional discrimination causes schools to apply and interpret policies in such a way that then creates school exclusions for specific students. Due to institutional discrimination, participants demonstrated the disadvantages for ethnic minorities such as the adultification which misrecognises and thus helps to criminalise their behaviour. This corresponds to Kulz’s study (2015) in the literature review who underlined adultification as an issue for ethnic minorities. Participants explain that the ‘unfair’ treatment and ‘neglect’ from teachers which is encouraged by institutional discrimination, is evident in children’s behaviour which is criminalised because of institutional discrimination. This is reiterated by one participant who said, *“teachers just react, react, react and just feed into behaviour rather than provide support in place”*. As a result, the ‘unmet needs’ of certain students continue to translate in their behaviour which is misinterpreted causing them to get excluded from school. Interviewees expressed that because of the exclusion the

child is disaffected and placed in a PRU where they meet other disaffected youths who have started to believe the labels placed onto them throughout the exclusion process.

4.5 Conclusion

To conclude, this chapter has analysed the data collected from the qualitative research study. It has been found that the experience of each participant supports the hypothesis; institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. Participants have suggested the notion of a pipeline could be decreased through strategies of social justice as it would counteract the effects of institutional discrimination. Participants recommended teachers investigate the cause(s) of behaviour, remove discriminatory school policies, and provide students the authority to question repercussions as this would allow their perspective of events to be respected. Moreover, disaffection from school has been highlighted as a key product in the adultification of Black youths in particular which participants view as heavily influenced by institutional discrimination.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

To conclude, this research aimed to answer if the public perceived institutional discrimination as contributory to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK. The literature review and the qualitative research carried out with a participant sample with direct knowledge or experience of school exclusions, has shown a consensus supporting the hypothesis. Institutional discrimination is presented as influential to the pipeline because it effects how students are responded to in the education and youth justice system. The inequality within the education system is reflected in the correlating figures of exclusion rates and youth incarceration rates. From the interviews, school exclusions have been highlighted as ineffective in disciplining behaviour as it is often on an individual basis rooted in discrimination rather than support for communication, social or learning needs.

Chapter two suggested that discriminatory policies and labelling of students and their actions by teachers are how institutional discrimination is prevalent in school exclusions. Chapter three outlined the methodology and the strengths and weaknesses in collected the data suggesting that qualitative primary research was best suited for this research study. Additionally, chapter four analysed the data collected and compared it to the literature review. Altogether this paper has suggested that there is a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK driven by institutional discrimination. As a result, specific children become disaffected from school leaving them vulnerable to criminality.

Based on these conclusions, the school system in the UK should review school exclusion policies and consider fair alternatives. Teachers need to be more inclusive of people's backgrounds and SEN children need more support in mainstream schools. Additionally, parents require further communication with schools and schools should analyse possible measures that can be taken before excluding a child from school. To further understand the implications of these results future research should include more Gypsy and Roma young people as they are disproportionately affected by a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline in the UK also. Furthermore, a longitudinal study including a racial and gendered variety of young people and parents would strengthen the hypothesis as validity would increase.

Additionally, the impact of PRUs has been demonstrated as negative because it cements feeling alienated and marginalised thus marking the start of a pipeline due to disaffection. The social learning theory has been put forward to explain the notion of a pipeline with its framework suggesting children behave according to what they observe and imitate. Therefore, the social learning theory supports the

hypothesis that institutional discrimination contributes to a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline as it theorises that a child observes and imitates the ideas the education system has on them. For example, treating Black kids as 'bad' influences the imitation of 'bad' behaviour which has been reiterated by participants. Consequently, the key recommendations are for the investment in abolishing school exclusions, promoting social justice through enforced compulsory anti-discriminatory teacher training, and having restorative conversations with children. It is only then that the public perceive that the notion of institutional discrimination in a school exclusion-to-youth offending pipeline can decrease.

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Appendix - Interview Schedule

Common interview questions:

1. Do teachers in secondary schools have the skills and support to support their students?
2. Does having learning support make a difference in pupil behaviour? (explain/reasons).
3. Do male and female students get treated differently in school?
4. Does coming from a low-income family affect students experiences in school?
5. What impact does school exclusion have on students who get excluded (temp + permanent)?
6. Are pupils excluded from school at higher risk of committing a crime (how?)
7. Is there a point in their schooling experiences at which students become at risk of offending? (Could you explain a bit more)?
8. How could/should school exclusions practices be improved?

Prompts:

- fairness
- success/effectiveness
- alternatives

Parents' additional interview questions:

1. How do you think the role of parenting changes as secondary school students get older? (Prompt for 'challenges + benefits for parents?')
2. How does parenting influence students' behaviour at school?
3. How can teachers work with parents to prevent school exclusions?
4. What do you think are the fears parents have once their child is excluded from school?

Is there anything you haven't said that you would like to?

Young adult additional interview questions:

1. In your experience, which students were more likely to get excluded and get excluded the most? (Prompt for particular identities)
2. In your experience, what reasons did students get excluded for the most? (Prompt for what they think about that (e.g., acceptable/trivial etc).
3. In your experience, were some teachers more likely to exclude students? (Prompt how would they describe teachers who did exclude?)
4. What do you think are the fears excluded students have? (Prompt for education related vs other concerns).

Is there anything you haven't said that you would like to?